

1 **Cell surface receptors expressed in HBV infection.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in a cell culture system modeling HBV infection in
7 primary human cells *in vitro*. Cells activated a network of cell surface receptors during hepatitis B infection.
8 These receptors and membrane proteins included *Tmem82*, *Tmem37* and *Tmem135*; *Fam162a*; *Ttc31*
9 and *Ttc39c*, as well as *Gpr88* and *Gpr180*. The genes encoded proteins that marked cells during active
10 infection: because they signaled to the immune system, or because they participated in some cellular
11 antiviral function.

12 Citations

13 1. Quintana, A., Sanz, E., Wang, W., Storey, G.P., Güler, A.D., Wanat, M.J., Roller, B.A., La Torre, A.,
14 Amieux, P.S., McKnight, G.S. and Bamford, N.S., 2012. Lack of GPR88 enhances medium spiny neuron
15 activity and alters motor-and cue-dependent behaviors. *Nature neuroscience*, 15(11), pp.1547-1555.

16 GSE183156